

UDC 658.5

**DEVELOPMENT OF THE STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF A
MEDICAL INSTITUTION IN THE CONTEXT OF HEALTHCARE
TRANSFORMATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN**

SMAGULOVA ZUBIRASH KALYBEKOVNA

Candidate of Economic Sciences, PhD, Associate Professor
Astana International University, Astana, Kazakhstan

ABDRAKHMANOVA ZHANAR UTEGENOVNA,

EMBA Master's Student of the Educational Program "Strategic Management and
Leadership", Astana International University, Astana, Kazakhstan

Abstract: *The article examines the issues of transforming the development strategy of a medical institution in order to improve management efficiency and the quality of medical services using the example of the Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "City Infectious Diseases Center" of the Akimat of Astana. The relevance of the study is обусловлена by the current processes of healthcare system reform in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the development of digitalization, increasing requirements for the quality of medical care, and the need to enhance the sustainability of medical organizations under epidemiological risks. The study analyzes the effectiveness of the management system of the medical institution, assesses the quality level of medical services, and identifies the main problems and limitations of the current development strategy. Particular attention is paid to digital transformation, the development of a patient-oriented approach, internal audit systems, prevention of professional burnout among medical personnel, and the implementation of ESG approaches in the management system of medical organizations. Based on the research results, directions for transforming the development strategy aimed at improving the quality of medical care, sustainability, and operational efficiency of the medical institution in modern conditions are proposed.*

Keywords: *strategic management, transformation, medical institution, quality of medical services, healthcare system, healthcare digitalization, management efficiency.*

Introduction. The modern healthcare system of the Republic of Kazakhstan operates in conditions of a highly dynamic external environment, digital transformation, increasing public demands for the quality of medical care, as well as the need to ensure the sustainability of medical organizations under epidemiological risks and limited resources. In recent years, the healthcare system of Kazakhstan has been undergoing a stage of large-scale transformation aimed at improving the accessibility, quality, and efficiency of medical services. The main directions of reform include healthcare digitalization, the implementation of compulsory social health insurance, the development of the infrastructure of medical organizations, and the transition to a patient-oriented healthcare model. State healthcare policy is focused on modernizing the management system of medical institutions, introducing modern medical technologies, and improving the professional competencies of healthcare personnel. Particular attention is paid to the development of e-health, including electronic medical records, telemedicine, and digital services for the population.

These challenges are especially relevant for specialized infectious disease institutions, whose activities are directly related to ensuring biological safety, efficiency in managerial decision-making, and the quality of medical services. The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated the need to revise traditional approaches to the strategic management of medical organizations. Under these conditions, there is an objective necessity to transform the existing development strategies of medical institutions in accordance with modern requirements for management efficiency, process digitalization, sustainable development, and patient orientation. The Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "City Infectious Diseases Center" of the Akimat of Astana is one of the key

specialized medical institutions providing diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of infectious diseases. In modern conditions, it is important for the institution not only to maintain a high level of medical care but also to implement modern strategic management mechanisms aimed at improving organizational efficiency and the quality of medical services.

The Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management “City Infectious Diseases Center” of the Akimat of Astana provides specialized medical care to the population in the field of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of infectious diseases. The main areas of the institution’s activities include inpatient medical care, infectious disease diagnostics, anti-epidemic activities, emergency medical services, and ensuring infectious safety of the population. The specific nature of the infectious disease center’s activities requires a high level of efficiency in managerial decision-making, sustainability of internal processes, and effective coordination of medical personnel.

It should be noted that the modern management system of medical organizations must ensure prompt decision-making, efficient use of resources, coordination of medical processes, management digitalization, and organizational sustainability under crisis conditions. The analysis of the infectious disease center’s activities demonstrates that the institution has both positive aspects of management and several problematic areas.

Strengths of the management system:

- availability of qualified medical personnel;
- experience in operating under epidemiological threats;
- state support for the institution;
- availability of specialized infrastructure.

Main problems:

- high workload on medical personnel;
- insufficient integration of digital technologies;
- limited flexibility of the management structure;
- insufficient level of automation of analytical processes;
- the need to improve the internal quality control system.

For a more comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of the management system in this institution, a SWOT analysis was conducted (table 1).

Table 1 – SWOT analysis of the municipal state enterprise on the right of economic management “City Infectious Diseases Center”

Strengths	Weaknesses
Specialized profile of the institution	High workload on personnel
Availability of experienced specialists	Bureaucratization of certain processes
State support	Insufficient analytical management system
High social significance of the institution	
Opportunities	Threats
Implementation of digital technologies	Increasing infectious risks
Development of telemedicine	Personnel shortage
Improvement of the quality of medical services	Epidemiological crises
Development of ESG approaches	

The conducted SWOT analysis demonstrates the necessity of transitioning to a more flexible and digitalized model of strategic management. The quality of medical services is one of the key indicators of the effectiveness of a medical institution’s activities. Under modern conditions, patients evaluate not only the treatment outcome but also the speed of medical assistance, accessibility of healthcare services, level of service, informational transparency, comfort, and safety.

To assess the quality of medical services, the following criteria can be identified:

- level of patient satisfaction;
- effectiveness of diagnostics and treatment;

- speed of medical care delivery;
- compliance with clinical protocols;
- level of digitalization of interaction with patients.

The analysis of the medical institution's activities shows that the main problems remain the high workload on admission departments, increased patient waiting times during epidemiological outbreaks, insufficient digital integration of medical processes, and limited analytical tools for quality assessment. At the same time, the institution has significant potential to improve the quality of medical services through the implementation of modern digital and managerial solutions. As a result of the conducted research, key directions for transforming the development strategy of the Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "City Infectious Diseases Center" were developed.

1. Digital Transformation of the Management System. One of the priority areas is the implementation of digital technologies: automation of management processes; implementation of electronic analytical systems; use of Big Data for forecasting epidemiological risks; development of telemedicine services.

Digitalization will increase the speed of managerial decision-making and reduce the administrative burden. As an example, the DamuMed information system in Kazakhstan can be considered. This platform was introduced to improve the accessibility of medical care, optimize the work of medical organizations, and enhance interaction between patients and healthcare institutions. The system makes it possible to automate appointment scheduling, maintain electronic medical records, obtain laboratory test results, issue referrals, and monitor patients' health conditions. The use of digital services contributes to reducing waiting times for medical care and increasing the transparency of medical institutions' activities. Under modern conditions, the DamuMed system is considered an important tool for improving management efficiency in the healthcare system of Kazakhstan. The platform ensures data integration, improves quality control of medical services, and enables prompt analysis of key performance indicators of medical organizations. At the same time, the further development of digital healthcare requires improvement of personal data protection, enhancement of the population's digital literacy, and expansion of the functional capabilities of medical information systems.

2. Implementation of Risk-Oriented Management. Risk management is of particular importance for infectious disease medical organizations. The following measures are proposed:

- creation of a system for monitoring epidemiological threats;
- implementation of crisis management protocols;
- formation of reserve management mechanisms;
- development of an internal audit system.

For example, the development of an internal audit system in medical institutions should be aimed at improving management efficiency, ensuring the quality of medical services, and reducing organizational risks. Internal audit makes it possible to conduct regular assessments of the activities of a medical organization, identify weaknesses in managerial and clinical processes, and monitor compliance with regulatory requirements and medical standards. Internal audit is especially important under conditions of high pressure on the healthcare system, when there is an increasing need for оперативный control over the quality of medical care, rational use of resources, and prevention of institutional errors. The effect of implementing and developing an internal audit system is reflected in increased transparency of management, improved quality of medical services, reduced financial and organizational losses, as well as increased patient trust in the medical institution. In addition, internal audit contributes to more efficient use of human, financial, and material resources, increases the level of staff responsibility, and helps ensure timely managerial decision-making based on an objective analysis of the organization's activities. In the long term, this ensures the sustainable development of the medical institution and enhances its competitiveness within the healthcare system.

3. Human Resource Development. The key resource of a medical organization is its personnel. Within the framework of strategic transformation, the following measures are proposed:

- advanced training and professional development of medical workers;
- development of leadership competencies among managers;
- implementation of professional burnout prevention programs;
- improvement of the personnel motivation system.

For a medical institution, professional burnout prevention programs are an important element in improving staff performance, the quality of medical services, and organizational sustainability. This is especially relevant for infectious disease centers, where employees work under conditions of high emotional and physical stress. Within the framework of professional burnout prevention in a medical institution, the following measures can be proposed: conducting training sessions on emotional resilience and stress management; implementing team-building and corporate support programs; optimizing work schedules and reducing excessive workload on medical personnel; creating rest and recovery rooms for employees; introducing staff rotation systems between departments to reduce emotional stress; implementing professional development and advanced training programs; providing non-material motivation for employees (recognition of achievements, gratitude, corporate awards); developing digital solutions that reduce paperwork and administrative burden; and regularly monitoring the level of staff satisfaction and emotional well-being.

The effect of implementing such programs is reflected in reduced staff turnover, increased employee motivation, improvement of the psychological climate within the team, and enhancement of the quality of medical care. In addition, prevention of professional burnout contributes to reducing the number of professional errors, increasing labor productivity, and strengthening the sustainability of medical institutions under crisis and epidemiological conditions.

4. Improving the Quality of Medical Services. In order to improve the quality of medical services, the following measures are proposed: implementation of a continuous patient satisfaction monitoring system; development of a patient-oriented approach; improvement of the internal quality control system; and optimization of patient routing processes. For example, medical organizations in Kazakhstan are actively implementing elements of digital services and patient feedback systems, including electronic queue management systems, mobile applications, SMS notifications, online consultations, and patient satisfaction assessment systems. In a number of medical institutions, the practice of service management is being developed, aimed at improving service quality, reducing bureaucratic procedures, and enhancing communication between doctors and patients. The digitalization of processes contributes to increasing the transparency of the healthcare system, improving the efficiency of medical care delivery, and enhancing the effectiveness of managerial decision-making.

5. ESG Approaches in the Development of a Medical Institution. Modern development strategies of medical organizations are increasingly based on ESG principles (Environmental, Social, Governance). For an infectious disease center, the most relevant areas include environmental safety of medical waste management, social responsibility towards patients and personnel, increasing transparency of management, and ensuring the sustainable development of the organization. Let us consider the model of transformation of a medical institution (Table 2).

Table 2 – Model for the transformation of the medical institution’s strategy

Stage	Content	Expected Result
Diagnostics	Analysis of the current state of the management system	Identification of problems and limitations
Digitalization	Implementation of digital solutions	Increased process efficiency
Management Optimization	Improvement of the organizational structure	Faster decision-making
Personnel Development	Improvement of qualifications and motivation	Growth in labor productivity

Quality Control	Implementation of KPI systems and monitoring	Improvement of service quality
Sustainable Development	Integration of ESG approaches	Long-term organizational sustainability

The conducted research demonstrates that under modern conditions, infectious disease medical institutions require the transformation of existing development strategies taking into account the processes of digitalization, increasing requirements for the quality of medical services, and the need to enhance the sustainability of the healthcare system. The analysis of the activities of the Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management “City Infectious Diseases Center” of the Akimat of Astana made it possible to identify a number of problems related to the high workload on personnel, limited digitalization of processes, and the need to improve the strategic management system. As a result of the research, directions for transforming the development strategy of the medical institution were developed, including digital transformation, implementation of risk-oriented management, development of human resources, improvement of the quality of medical services, and integration of ESG approaches. The implementation of the proposed measures will make it possible to improve the efficiency of medical institution management, enhance the quality of medical services, increase the organization’s resilience to external threats, and ensure the long-term development of the medical institution.

Thus, the transformation of the development strategy of a medical institution acts as an important tool for improving the efficiency of the healthcare system and the quality of medical care provided to the population. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the strategic transformation of medical organizations is becoming especially significant due to the need to adapt the healthcare system to new socio-economic, demographic, and epidemiological challenges. The development of digital technologies, implementation of compulsory social health insurance, and increasing public expectations regarding the quality of medical services require medical institutions to transition to more flexible, sustainable, and patient-oriented management models.

REFERENCES:

1. Ansoff I. Strategic Management. – Moscow: Ekonomika, 2009. – 519 p.
2. Vikhansky O.S. Strategic Management: Textbook. – Moscow: Gardariki, 2018. – 296 p.
3. Golubkov E.P. Strategic Management: Textbook and Practical Guide. – Moscow: Yurait, 2021. – 290 p.
4. Daft R.L. Organization Theory and Organizational Behavior. – Saint Petersburg: Piter, 2020. – 624 p.
5. Kotler P., Shalowitz J., Stevens R. Strategic Marketing for Health Care Organizations. – Moscow: GEOTAR-Media, 2019. – 496 p.
6. Nazarenko G.I., Polubentseva E.I. Quality Management of Medical Care. – Moscow: Meditsina, 2017. – 320 p.
7. Salimova T.A. Quality Management: Textbook. – Moscow: Omega-L, 2020. – 376 p.
8. State Program for Healthcare Development of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020–2025. – Astana, 2020. – 98 p.
9. Address of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan “Kazakhstan in a New Reality: Time for Action”. – Astana, 2020. – 24 p.
10. Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan: Official Website. – Available at: Ministry of Healthcare of the Republic of Kazakhstan (accessed: 09.05.2026).
11. DamuMed: Digital Healthcare Management System in Kazakhstan (accessed: 09.05.2026).
12. Municipal State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management “City Infectious Diseases Center” of the Akimat of Astana: Official Website (accessed: 09.05.2026).